

LINGUISTICS AND THE TEACHING OF SPOKEN ENGLISH A LITERATURE REVIEW OF THEORETICAL ANCHORS AND EMPIRICAL STUDIES

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Abstract

This paper is designed to identify the impact of linguistics in the teaching of spoken English. The current study uses a fundamentally educational-linguistic approach as it has a basic framework in English language teaching (ELT). The study uses a descriptive research and it uses the critical bibliographic literature review and the qualitative methods. In this study, the researcher focuses on secondary data, notably content analysis to come up with viable outcomes. This study will assess linguistics in the teaching of spoken English using a qualitative approach. It's fair to assume that linguistics is the biggest topic in the minds of English teachers. Linguistics is important when learning English, especially in the ELT context. Linguistics has a significant impact on English teaching. The history of the teaching of spoken English is intertwined with a variety of linguistic disciplines. In the field of linguistics, teachers are better able to convey not just the meaning and historical context of words and languages, but also their contemporary relevance. More and more, linguistics is being used in the classroom, and it's often in interdisciplinary ways. Not only do language instructors use it, but so do educators in fields like sociology, anthropology, and children's development. Understanding the rules and regulations of language, both written and spoken, and the context in which words are used is what linguistics is all about. The study of idioms and regional languages is another area that linguistics helps students with. Additionally, it helps students find the origins of expressions that have changed throughout time but may no longer have any real significance.

Keywords: Spoken English; Linguistics; Language; Teaching; English language Teaching.

INTRODUCTION

Finding out how linguistics relates to the field of English language instruction is the driving force behind this study. The paper goes on to highlight the significance of linguistics and the English language. The study employs the critical bibliographic method for reviewing research. In addition, the study also explained the fundamental principle of linguistics.

In recent years, it has been seen that the English language has gained enormous popularity over the world (Abdurasulovich & Rajabovich, 2019). Also, in worldwide trade, commerce and tourism, English has also become increasingly important. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that English has become the universal language. Consequently, hundreds of thousands of teachers daily focus on English to fulfill the demands of such a large population, and the demand for this language is growing at an exponential pace. The article goes on to say that learning English, especially spoken English, may help students in many other areas, but especially in college. Having a solid grasp of linguistics is essential for instructors who want to provide their pupils more advanced lesson plans. The field known as linguistics examines how languages come to be, how they are structured, how they are spoken, how they have changed over time, and how these aspects have been shaped by social, historical, and

anthropological factors (Al Zoubi, 2018). Thus, as communicators, education specialists, and evaluators, English instructors should have complete authority over linguistics (Almutairi, 2021). If you want to be a successful teacher who can connect with pupils from all walks of life, you need to work on your public speaking skills. In order for educators to effectively organize and convey information to their pupils, they need take on the role of their own communications designers. Linguistics is extremely important for teaching teachers because education is constantly evolving these days. Classes are becoming increasingly diverse, with more students from different ethnic backgrounds, and most importantly speaking the English language. Hence, Peoples who speak English are better able to assist and even interact with each other.

Possessing strong English communication skills opens you additional job opportunities. Employees with strong English communication skills are in high demand by businesses. English also allows businesses to connect with a wider range of prospective customers online. In the United States and other English-speaking countries, those who are unable to communicate in English have a substantial economic disadvantage. Linguistics is crucial in this regard, as English is comparatively easy to pick up and use since it is based on a simple alphabet.

Research questions

- How linguistics relates to the English language?
- What is the importance of linguistics and the English Language?
- What are the Linguistic principles of teaching English?

Research objectives

- To better understand how linguistics relates to ESL classrooms
- To acknowledge the role of linguistics in ESL instruction

Significance of the study

This research study's main objective is to investigate the relationship between linguistics in English spoken teaching. It should be highlighted that the current study's main focus is on the shape of teaching spoken English, the nature of grammar in spoken or conversational English. As a result, it focuses on 'teaching spoken English. This study shows that introducing linguistics aid in opportune learning development and increased student capability in all English language abilities, reading, and conversation.

This research study will be helpful for individuals who want to learn English. Finally, this research proposal can help people with relevant information about linguistics. Due to the sheer significance of the current research study, it is possible to gather all relevant and precise data based on the research questions. Finally, the generated data is intended to be used as a resource for scholars seeking knowledge. It can also be utilised as a framework for a comprehensive examination of the teaching and education sector as a critical component of any modern teaching infrastructure.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Importance of English language

Language is extremely important in the evolution of human society. It is the main source of communication for individuals, communities, and nations. The English language has developed into a global language says Chouit, (2021). English is largely spoken and learned in over 120 countries, and it is extensively employed as a business or diplomatic language. Hence, more than 400 million people all around the world speak English as their first language. People all over the world have used the English language to communicate in order to listen to broadcasts, read articles, news, magazines, newspapers, and books, and travel to different regions of the world, among other activities. It has proved to be an extremely successful connecting language across worldwide.

Millions of people study English as a second language since it is the most widely spoken language in the world. There have been efforts to make English classes more productive in this area. Teaching English as a second language has grown in importance as a means to empower individuals to communicate effectively in written and spoken forms (Mann & Walsh, 2017). It has also been noted that English is vital in the field of education. Learning English as a second language is something that many nations emphasize and support for children. At the university level, students from a number of countries learn almost entirely in English. The majority of the web, at 95%, is written and published in English. English is the most widely used language in the media, with more books and articles written in it than any other language. Students will have a leg up in practically any field if they can converse in English, given the language's widespread use in global communication. English is perhaps the most accessible language in the world in terms of learning materials.

In today's world, the English language is vital for many reasons. According to Dutta, first and foremost, it is the language that foreigners use the most (2019). This implies that English is often chosen as a lingua franca when two persons from different countries (for instance, a Chinese and a Swede) converse. Therefore, in order to communicate globally, everyone needs learn the language. It will facilitate interaction with individuals from all corners of the earth.

Furthermore, one's ability to communicate in English will also benefit them in any commercial venture they pursue. For example, if one goes to some offices, businesses, government agencies, or even math or engineering firms, they will realize how important English is. As per Clement, & Murugavel, (2018), any large corporation will employ its professional personnel after determining whether or not the individuals are fluent in English. According to Jabbarova, (2020), companies that want to operate on a global scale only consider their employees to be well qualified and they are fluent in English and can write, read, and write well. In brief, Learning English not only enhances one's standard of living, but also one's personal growth, which is why education is so important. For example, anyone can assess an international career and can live in a variety of nations with the ease of going shopping, interacting or negotiating a house lease. Besides, it is not wrong to say scholars who want to get good careers should focus on their English and how they use it since their career depends on this core structure.

In the views of Krebt, (2017), there is no shortage of ways in which they improve one's command of the English language. One of the several barriers that the English language is able to transcend is cultural differences. People can relate to each other and hence comprehend one other thanks to the English language.

People can relate to each other and hence comprehend one other thanks to the English language. Consistent use, watching films, reading books with advanced grammar, playing video games, and attempting to employ new terms are all ways of improving English. Practice will help people improve their English. Mamadiyorova, (2021) recognised that, in today's world, English is unquestionably necessary for communication. It becomes a tool for learning and mastering diverse disciplines.

Therefore, students are interested in English speaking because they need to gain the confidence to confront a large group of people in interviews if they want to advance in their careers. Also, it argues that it's also quite difficult to survive in today's world without knowing English.

Figure 1, depicts the reasons why the English language is important.

Figure 1: the importance of the English language

(Source: Self-made)

Importance of linguistics

The scientific study of languages is Linguistics, and it is extremely imperative for learners and teachers (Spolsky, 2019). Language comprehension comprises not only the structure and meaning of words but also their use in both spoken and written forms. The field of linguistics provides teachers with tools for explaining not just the meaning and history of words and languages, but also how these concepts have evolved over time (Matkasimova & Makhmudov, 2020). This teaching approach allows students to develop a deeper insight into the language and expected work products. As a result, the skills needed to sustain and develop the art of reading, writing, and communication are provided by teaching and studying linguistics. This is vital in the curriculum, in the job, and the community. In addition, Linguistics is also crucial when it comes to understanding the variations between conversational and academic language, as well as abstract norms concerning word usage in other cultures (Thao & Tai, 2017).

The study of language and communication is alluded to as linguistics. It is concerned with the study of specific languages as well as the search for general features that are shared among all languages. It is divided into the following sections:

- *Phonetics*: the study of the construction, audibility and hearing of speech echoes
- *Phonology*: the study of sound patterns
- *Morphology*: the word formation / structure of sentences
- *Syntax*: research of the processes by which morphemes and words come together to produce sentences and other bigger units
- *Semantics*: the study of word meaning
- *Pragmatics*: the study of language in context

Additionally, it delves into the nature of linguistic diversity (tongues), the temporal development of languages, the brain's processing and storage of languages, and the learning process. In addition, linguists investigate how words are learned, how this information is integrated with other mental capacities, how it varies between languages and areas, and how to effectively communicate this knowledge (Vitalievna, 2021).

They investigate the interplay between the many parts of language, how to cognitively account for different linguistic patterns, and how to articulate the structures of different parts of language (such as sounds or meaning). A linguist is a scientist who develops and tests theories in the field of science. Many linguists use mathematical formalities, statistical analysis, and statistical analysis to describe the patterns they see.

Knowledge of semantics can help learners grasp the arbitrary relationship between words and meaning, as well as how and why dialects divide the world the way they do, and the sensory and cognitive mechanisms that people use to learn and convey meaning.

Figure 2: Significance of Linguistics

(Source: Self-made)

The relationship between linguistics and English language teaching

Learning to speak and write English fluently and efficiently is the holy grail of English language classes. A coach, mediator, or advisor may help students achieve this goal, but only if he gives them opportunities to experiment, ask questions, and voice their opinions. Speaking English as a foreign language requires a diverse set of abilities and strategies, according to Pulatova (2021). As the principal means of communication and the "capability" to acquire a new language, speaking is an integral part of every language curriculum. A speaker's knowledge and abilities must be actively engaged in real-time when speaking English, which necessitates the simultaneous activation of several processes (cognitive, physiological, and socio-cultural).

Therefore, linguistics plays a significant role in ESL classrooms since it helps educators better convey the language's structure and components to their pupils. The field of linguistics is used by educators to guide pupils in comprehending the elements of speech, the fundamental skills necessary for processing and producing speech, and effective communication techniques for navigating conversations (Xamrayeva, 2020).

Teachers of spoken English would do well to draw on linguistics, the scientific study of language, as a tool in their classrooms. Experts in the field of language may provide light on the workings of any given language. The ability to choose instructional reading materials, journals, audio-video tape recorders and cassettes, self-access, and digital language training is

crucial for English instructors who want to improve their students' language acquisition. To help students succeed in and out of class, it's important that their language production be well-planned and expressive. Therefore, one may argue that language and linguistics are inseparable. Moreover, the rules of each language like English vary depending on the activity, the medium used (spoken or written), the roles of the people, the conversation, the tasks and purposes, etc. The English Language requires grammatical ability and communicative ability states Rao, (2019). Teaching English as a spoken language mostly involves grammar. The rules of grammar may provide light on how the English language is structured. Nouns, verbs, articles, consonants, adjectives, and a host of other essential components of speech must also be taught to pupils.

Linguistics aid English teachers in teaching vocabulary with grammatical explanations to students. English teacher allows students to advance their grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation skills, so they can speak English fluently. The tools for expressing semantic and pragmatic significance are provided by grammatical structure and vocabulary, which are interconnected in their communication. In the opinion of Rungruangthum & Jumpakate, (2021), a stronger understanding of linguistics will teachers see that the speech forms they favour are traits of their own culture and background. If teachers do not understand the cultural differences, they will not recognise the way kids use language, and they may not anticipate children to use language totally, resulting it makes more complicated issues. If teachers are unable to recognise the success of other modes of communication, their students' confidence in their own abilities to communicate may be shaken. This is why having linguistic expertise is critical so that neither the kid nor the educator gets confused during communication. As a result, linguistics can help English teachers prepare to engage with students from a range of diverse, social, and linguistic backgrounds. Their interpretation of language would most likely differ from that of a native- English speaker, which is an important issue to consider when teaching. Shaykhislamov & Makhmudov, (2020) determined that it is also reasonable to state that Language and linguistics are critical components of the teaching process. It has a significant progressive impact throughout the student's educational career, regardless of cultural, social, or linguistic variances. A contrastive semantic study can reveal to teachers, why speakers in English mix their pronouns. Besides, knowledge of semantics enables the teacher to foresee potential problems in spoken English. This sub-division of linguistics help students in building vocabulary. As per Spolsky, (2019), Linguistics has proved the importance of English language understanding beyond the sentence level. Concepts like paragraph structure, clarity and continuity, and the framework of a text and the purposes of its constituent parts were useful in developing the capacity to produce and read.

As a result, teachers are playing an increasingly important role in language development, which extends beyond teaching students how to speak and write. It is found that the teacher provides designed numerous frameworks and tools, which includes online games, quizzes, reading exercises, and grammatical reference modules, this will help the students to speak English easily and correctly. The important components of language related to the academic syllabus of the various topic courses are used by English Language teachers. Besides, Linguistics assists teachers in developing successful and innovative educational resources of instruction that allow

students to explore novel forms and styles of presentation. This is why, in order to support language progress with all children in their careers, teachers must have an understanding of educational linguistics. Teachers must help students become more aware of the linguistic functions in forms of communication throughout the course. This signifies a thorough understanding of linguistics can aid in the liberation of both teachers and students. In a nutshell, it's safe to say that students from all over the world, regardless of their socioeconomic status, ethnic origin, or language proficiency, will be able to communicate effectively in English when their teachers have a solid grasp of linguistics and practice what they preach.

How teachers help students in speaking the English language

It is critical to devote time in the classroom to all modes of communication, including interpretative, interpersonal, and communicational, but interpersonal communication should be the primary focus. It has been found that there are many activities that teachers employ in their teaching while speaking English. For example, as a part of the activity teacher makes slips with different topics and scenarios. The teacher distributes the slip among students. Thus, based on the topic students have to practice a conversation on the topic. After that, each student should go to the front of the classroom and speak for three or five minutes about their theme. However, Various factors impact the end result of a language study, including background knowledge, attitudes, personality traits, learning styles, abilities, and motivation, which are all taken into account while instructing students in English. In particular circumstances, education should be adjusted by student needs and objectives. The mindset that underpins cooperative learning is accepting of one another's differences as well as a readiness to share and promote one another's learning in whatever methods are most suitable (Matkasimova & Makhmudov, 2020).

Students and teachers, as well as learners among themselves, must achieve a comfort level with one another, in order to create an engaged language-learning environment. Consequently, teachers must be comfortable with what they're doing, just as learners must be comfortable in order to create this balance. More than precisely handled structures and lexicon, pronounced with comprehensible sounds and intonation, are required in English communication. It also necessitates adherence to the established forms of natural conversation in the connected culture: Students must be able to start and conclude conversational interludes, negotiate to mean, assert communicative command, fill pauses, intervene or not disrupt, and manoeuvre within the interaction so that the conversation is directed in the interlocutor's preferred direction (Zengin, Başal, & Yükselir, 2019). Linguistic has had a significant impact on English education. The following are a few linguistic principles that apply to the English language:

Principle 1: *Sound's Importance* - Sounds are a language's most core pillar. As a result, when teaching English, the accents of the language should take precedence. English sentences should be delivered with suitable intonation and rhythm. They should appear in suitable expressions and sentences that are pronounced with the same intonation and rhythm as a native speaker.

Principle 2: *Context and Settings are Crucial* - Different aspects of the language, including vocabulary and structures, should be discussed in the context of real-life circumstances so that the learner can relate to them.

Principle 3: *Controlled Vocabulary* - English vocabulary should be studied in a controlled setting. Simple words should be taught first, followed by harder ones, as appropriate for the student's age and ability (Uou.ac.in. 2021). Students can simply progress from short utterances to lengthier phrases. The principle allows students to obtain a better understanding of the English language material in terms of sounds and vocabulary.

Principle 4: *Categorised Patterns* - This refers to the idea of teaching English patterns in graded phases. Each new pattern should be added to the base ones by the teacher. Make linguistic patterns a habit by putting them to use in a range of contexts. Students should be taught how to communicate using language patterns and sentence constructs with acceptable vocabulary. The regular usage of the most commonly utilised patterns and elements of language, rather than the simple accrual of words, should take priority.

Principle 5: *Selection and gradation* - This involves teaching initially those sentence patterns whose application can be demonstrated in the classroom through visible actions. As a result, the student will gain a better understanding of the language in relation to the action. Only real-life events should be used to teach and practise vocabulary. The meaning will be clarified and reinforced in this manner.

Principle 6: *Language Skills Priorities* - There are 4 elements: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Listening should proceed to talk, communicating to reading, and reading to writing. Reading and writing are secondary abilities, but listening and speaking are primary. They serve to reinforce what has been learned through comprehension and communication. In reality, understanding help to speed up speaking skill.

Principle 7: *Oral approach* - This is the next linguistic principle in Teaching English. Hearing and tongue are more essential in language than sight. Every human being begins by hearing and speaking in order to learn a language.

Principle 8: *Formation of Language Interference* - When learning English as a second language, it is necessary to form new ways in daily activities.

Principle 9: *Use of Mother Tongue* - This means that the mother tongue can be used to describe some things at a native stage. During the time when English is being taught, students should not speak in their native language.

Principle 10: *Accuracy* - Inaccuracies in pronunciation, spelling, and writing are difficult to communicate, hence accuracy is essential in speaking the English language. When learning English, one must try to replicate the sounds, patterns, and modes of utterance.

Principle 11: *Maxims* - These maxims apply not just to the study of English, but also the study of any language. While teaching English, the English teacher should maintain those maxims in view.

Principle 12: *Natural method of Teaching* - This idea states that teachers should follow the natural process of learning a language when teaching English.

Principle 13: *Stable Approach* - This principle emphasises the importance of using a balanced approach when teaching. If a teacher only teaches grammar and overlooks other components of the language. Hence, teaching English would be difficult.

Figure 3: Principles of Linguistic

(Source: Self-made)

Outline of Research Methodology

Research Methods

The research methods of the study are as follows-

- The researcher employed the “Critical bibliographic review” to comprehensively explore the study topics and generate meaningful solutions.
- Collection and evaluation of secondary data derived from appropriate case studies, reports and prior analysis in studies to produce fruitful results and findings.
- The author critically reviews all the researchers, papers, and studies to recognise the significance of language and linguistics.

RESULTS/FINDINGS

Objectives of the study	Verdicts/ Results
<i>Importance of linguistics</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Languages, including their syntax, morphology, and speech in context, are the subject of linguistics, the scientific study of languages. • Linguistics might provide very easy ways to teach the illiterate to read and write, as well as solve all the issues related to teaching English as a spoken language. • Understanding the distinctions between academic and conversational language, as well as the cultural norms around word use, requires a strong grasp of language. • Linguists investigate the processes by which people acquire a vocabulary, how this knowledge interacts with other cognitive abilities, how it differs across speakers and regions, and how to articulate this information clearly.
<i>Importance of English language</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Students may expand their job opportunities and interact with people from different parts of the globe by learning English. ▪ English has gotten extremely crucial for inter-state trade and communication, in terms of international commerce. ▪ English language is a key part of the school curriculum, and it serves as a potent language of communication that serves as a strong unifying force for all of the various factions.
<i>An examination of linguistics and its use in ESL classrooms</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Because it helps instructors explain the parts and structures of English to students, linguistics plays a crucial role in English language education. All languages, including English, have a set of teachable rules governing phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics. ▪ Understanding proficiency in linguistics is the primary stage in training students to speak the English language well. ▪ Researchers in the field of language assist educators in developing fresh and engaging lesson plans that provide students the freedom to try out different approaches to content delivery. ▪ Linguistics assist English teachers in teaching vocabulary to pupils together with grammatical explanations.
<i>The relationship between linguistics and English language teaching</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Linguistics' focus on language in culture and society gives teachers useful information for teaching English. ▪ To help their pupils fully grasp syntactic systems, English instructors might rely on linguistics. ▪ The significance of encouraging pupils to discuss the language and discover its general structure on their own is recognized by a linguist who has completed teacher training. ▪ Linguistics can assist English teachers in preparing to work with pupils from a variety of social, linguistic, and cultural backgrounds. ▪ Teachers will see that the speech types they like are characteristics of their own culture and background if they have a better understanding of linguistics.

CONCLUSION

As a result of its status as a universal language and lingua franca, English is known to be spoken by almost every country on Earth. Numerous nations, including the UK, AU, USA, Canada, NL, NZ, and the Caribbean, have English as their official language, and millions of native speakers live and work there. When it comes to international business meetings and the majority of trade deals, English is by far the most used language. Possessing impeccable English is not only a sign of sophistication, but it also opens doors to pursuing further degrees at prestigious institutions in countries where English is the official language.

Learning English not only enhances one's quality of life, but education is also crucial for personal growth. Consequently, one may easily reside in many countries while evaluating a global career. Because English is a universal language, students are able to connect with and understand one another. Because it aids instructors in explaining the components and structures of the English language to students, linguistics is fundamental to the field of English language education and, more specifically, to the instruction of oral communication skills. It is possible to acquire the phonetics, phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics of any language. But pedagogy for teaching English as a second language should draw from a variety of disciplines, including sociology, anthropology, cognitive science, psychology, and bilingualism.

In addition, it is determined that linguistics is concerned with both the study of individual languages and the search for characteristics shared by all languages. The course also delves into the history of languages, their development over time, the brain's role in language processing, and the ways in which pupils pick up new languages. Moreover, the study explains the fundamentals of linguistics, which aids educators in their pursuit of excellence in English language instruction. Teachers of English must ensure that their lessons help students achieve their goals. Therefore, it is essential to have a solid grounding in the fundamentals of English language instruction. Teaching speaking is an often-overlooked yet crucial part of teaching English as a second language.

It has been determined that teaching of spoken English requires a diverse set of abilities and strategies. Linguistics assist English teachers in teaching vocabulary to pupils together with grammatical explanations. Grammar can help one comprehend the structure of the English language, such as nouns, verbs, articles, consonants, adjectives, and a few other things. It has also been found from the investigating the study that the value of comprehending the English language beyond the sentence level has been demonstrated by linguistics. Paragraph organisation, clarity, and consistency are all helpful in developing the ability to write and read. Teachers can learn why English speakers mix the word classes using a contrastive semantic study or contrastive analysis. According to the results, children often have difficulties with both hearing and speaking. The demands of both listening and speaking, as well as the relative nature of most approaches to teaching speech, contribute to this. Typically, it's used to drill a particular grammatical point or includes language practice activities like debates and information-gap exercises. There isn't a single one of those activities that teaches real-world interaction patterns.

Consequently, it is essential that we ascertain the needs of learners and provide them with realistic and practical contact. Teachers of English as a second language also have a responsibility to help their students develop an awareness of the role language plays in different forms of expression. Providing children with ongoing feedback and incorporating spoken language practice into specific tasks might help achieve this goal. Also, getting to know pupils is key to assisting them in becoming fluent speakers of English. As a result, needs analysis is crucial so that educators may better understand their students' requirements, gaps, and desires in the classroom.

Overgeneralization of the target language, language transfer, techniques of foreign language communication, and learning strategies for the foreign language are the most common causes of learners' semantic mistakes while speaking, according to research. Along these lines, the researcher draws the conclusion that learners also acquire a second language by drawing on prior knowledge to overcome communication barriers. It turns out that reading couldn't happen if humans couldn't comprehend language. We now know that all languages have five fundamental components. Among these branches are pragmatics, semantics, phonology, syntax, and morphology. Acquiring a language develops throughout these domains as proficiency, use, knowledge, and capacity all rise. How one's linguistic abilities evolve is defined by each of these factors. The aforementioned five factors affect the learning of grammar, vocabulary, and speaking skills, and there are some parallels and variances across languages that impact these areas. Researchers in the field of linguistics and speech education have shown that students need to know that informal spoken language is simpler than written language.

More "vague" or generalized language is used, sentences are shorter, and organization is lacking. In addition, students must have access to a range of spoken text kinds, be able to adapt to various listening scenarios, pronounce words well, follow continuous speech, and practice is key. Understanding the combinatorial nature of speaking is essential for competent speaking teachers. This nature encompasses: a) the linguistic and discoursal aspects of speech, b) the fundamental speaking abilities that allow speakers to process and produce speech, and c) the communication strategies for managing and maintaining spoken interactions. All levels of education should make public speaking a mandatory part of their course syllabi and expected achievements. Teachers would do well to familiarize themselves with the components of speaking competence and their interrelationships in order to impart this information in a way that is both thorough and holistic. To wrap things up, it's important to note that instructors need to work on creating effective communication tactics and projects that cater to students' varying levels of speaking ability.

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